

1 **Can trees and their associated organisms still benefit arable crops in the presence of pesticide use?**

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3 Colin R Tosh^{1*} and Jo Smith²

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5 1. The Organic Research Centre, Trent Lodge, Stroud Road, Cirencester, Gloucestershire, GL7 6JN, UK
6 colin.t@organicresearchcentre.com

7 2. Moinhos de Vento Agroecological Research Centre (MVarc), Beja, Mértola, 7750-217 Espirito
8 Santo, Portugal josmith@mvarc.eu

9

10 *Corresponding author: colin.t@organicresearchcentre.com

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33 **Abstract**

34 1. CONTEXT

35 Trees growing in and around the field (agroforestry) attract a range of organisms and empirical
36 studies indicate that these are overall beneficial to the arable crop. A recently modelling study of
37 English organic silvoarable using a new approach based on Boolean regulatory network modelling
38 supported this conclusion.

39 2. OBJECTIVE

40 Here we develop this model further to consider the impact of pesticide use on the benefits trees can
41 bring to crops through living interactions.

42 3. METHODS

43 Pests in the model agroecosystem are selectively and non-selectively removed from the
44 agroecosystem under a range of intervention thresholds to simulate pesticide use, and the benefits
45 of trees quantified and compared to benefits accrued under a baseline treatment of no pesticide
46 use.

47 4. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

48 Selective interventions for crop disease and crop insects (pests and non-target natural enemies)
49 dramatically reduce the benefits of trees, even at relatively high intervention thresholds.
50 Intervention for crop weeds increases the benefits of trees, as weeds are often considered a burden
51 associated with tree understories. Less selective, double interventions (weed-disease, weed-pest-
52 natural enemy, disease-pest-natural enemy) all reduce the benefits of trees, but the weed-pest-
53 natural enemy intervention least so. Unsurprisingly, removing all living associates of trees renders
54 trees of no benefit to crop yield through biotic mechanisms but, more surprisingly, this conclusion
55 applies when intervention thresholds are high and delayed to late in the growing season.

56 5. SIGNIFICANCE

57 Caution is urged in the interpretation of model findings but this study provides a first guide to how
58 pesticide use in agroforestry systems modulates the benefits of trees. These findings may be
59 particularly useful to growers in the increasingly popular area of regenerative agriculture which
60 permits restrained and selective use of pesticides.

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69 Introduction

70 Many countries and political unions across the world have ambitious tree planting strategies as part
71 of their climate amelioration strategy (Mosquera-Losada et al., 2023; Westaway et al., 2023). Due to
72 the high percentage of land covered by agriculture in most industrialised countries this necessarily
73 involves strategic planting in or around agricultural land (agroforestry). However, the expansion of
74 agroforestry is more than simple “spillover” and this land use is recognised for its high productivity
75 and multifunctional benefits and is being specifically incentivised accordingly (USDA 2011;
76 Government of India et al. 2014; Mosquera-Losada et al. 2023; Westaway et al. 2023).

77 Trees exert effects on arable crops through both abiotic/biophysical and biotic mechanisms. Trees
78 compete biophysically with crops for light, water and nutrients but they can create favourable
79 microclimates within the field and so protect crops from environmental extremes (Dobhal et al.,
80 2024; Nasielski et al., 2015; Reyes et al., 2021) which are increasingly problematic under climate
81 change (Seneviratne et al. 2021). Biotic mechanisms operate through the organisms that trees bring
82 with them (insects, understory plants etc) and the interaction of these organisms with the crop. In
83 tropical systems agroforestry reduces weed incidence and increases natural enemy abundance
84 (Pumariño et al., 2015). Positive effects on incidence of crop pests and disease are, however, only
85 significant in perennial crops (Pumariño et al., 2015). In temperate silvoarable trees boost natural
86 enemy abundance and reduce herbivorous insect abundance but potentially increase the incidence
87 of molluscan pests. Trees also increase the abundance of pollinators (Kletty et al., 2023; Staton et al.,
88 2019). Pumariño et al. (2015), Staton et al. (2019) and Kletty et al. (2023) all consider the overall
89 effect of trees on arable crops through biotic mechanisms “positive”.

90 This was also the conclusion reached by Tosh et al. (2024) in the first theoretical analysis of the
91 impacts of trees on crops through biotic mechanisms. Using a new theoretical approach called
92 GBRNM based on Boolean regulatory network modelling (Kauffman, 1969, 1993; Shmulevich et al.,
93 2002) it was predicted that the biotic interactions of tree in English organic silvoarable boost arable
94 crop yield but do not increase yield stability to biotic stress such as disease or pest outbreaks.

95 The current article continues to explore the dynamics of the GBRNM model of Tosh et al. (2024) to
96 investigate the extent to which pesticide use negates the benefits of trees through biotic
97 mechanisms. Insects, crop disease and crop weeds are selectively and non-selectively removed from
98 the agroecosystem under a range of intervention thresholds and the benefits of trees to arable crop
99 yield quantified and compared to benefits accrued under the baseline treatment of no pesticide use.
100 This study runs straight to the heart of the current debate on the relative merits of organic and
101 regenerative agriculture (Rempelos et al. 2023; Soil Association 2024) as regenerative agriculture
102 allows pesticide use (typically in a selective and restricted way) but organic agriculture does not. Can
103 growers still expect to receive biotic ecosystem services from trees if they use pesticides, even in a
104 selective way? What pesticide interventions least and most negate tree-based ecosystem services?
105 Will increasing application thresholds improve ecosystem service provision if growers are using
106 pesticides? These are some of the questions addressed by this study. Previous work (Tosh et al.
107 2024) has indicated that crop yield is very sensitive to crop disease and least sensitive to pest natural
108 enemies, so we hypothesise that crop disease intervention will substantially reduce any crop yield-
109 related tree benefits that may exist. We assume these benefits can be restored by increasing disease
110 intervention threshold (“spraying less”) but it is not clear if these benefits can be restored within an
111 intervention threshold range that would be acceptable to the grower. Hypothesising with regard to
112 natural enemies is complicated here because we assume non-selective insecticide treatment for
113 crop pests that knocks out both insect pests and their main insect natural enemies in concert.

114 Generally speaking, hypothesis generation on the behaviour of model networks is difficult as these
115 systems can have complex emergent dynamics. The modeller genuinely has little idea what will
116 emerge from networks and this makes such systems interesting and rewarding to work with. Lastly,
117 we urge caution in the interpretation of findings. While GBRNM models output plausible
118 agroecosystem dynamics (Tosh et al. 2024) they have not yet been field validated. Nevertheless, as
119 many nations are currently undergoing a rapid shift to an ecosystem service-based model of field
120 management we feel that any objective guidance we can offer growers on maximising ecosystem
121 service provision should be welcomed.

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123 **Methods**

124 The modelling methods summarised here are described fully in Tosh et al. (2024). The system
125 described by our model is shown in Figure 1. The model represents the influence of in-field trees on
126 arable yield, mediated through the biotic (living) parts of the agroecosystem. Direct effects of trees
127 through biophysical competition for water, light, and nutrients are systematically excluded as they
128 have been modelled elsewhere (Dupraz et al., 2019; van der Werf et al., 2007). We use a relatively
129 new modelling technique in agricultural science called GBRNM (Generalised Boolean Regulatory
130 Network Modelling - Tosh et al. 2024) derived from Boolean regulatory network modelling of gene
131 networks. The fundamental characteristic of this technique is that network members (“nodes”, see
132 Figure 1) can only exist in one of two states: high or low, good or bad, present or absent etc. This
133 simplifies the time dynamic parameterisation of the model to interpretation of a series of Boolean
134 logic statements. For example, one such statement might read: crop disease is currently low, in-field
135 trees are present, crop weeds are currently low, crop pests are currently high. What is the
136 probability of crop disease changing from low to high in a week’s time? One hundred and twenty-
137 eight such unique statements completely describe the time-dynamics of the system shown in Figure
138 1. Ideally, probabilities in these statements would be determined from careful field studies and we
139 aim to field-parameterise the model in the future. However, in the absence of such data currently,
140 we have turned to experts. Five of the leading experts in English organic silvoarable have provided
141 probabilities for time dynamic logic statements, having first been presented a text passage which
142 gives further context to the interactions in Figure 1. In essence, these interactions are assumed to
143 occur in an English, organic arable system with or without in field tree rows, with minimally
144 managed tree understories where tree rows occur (see Tosh et al. (2024) for a full description of the
145 nature of the system envisaged). One additional expert has completed the parameterisation exercise
146 since Tosh et al. (2024). She is co-author on the current paper and a short biography of this expert is
147 presented in the Supplementary Information (see Tosh et al. (2024) for biographies of the other
148 experts). Three of five experts were naïve as to the purpose of the exercise at the time of
149 completion, one was partially naïve, and one was fully aware of the purpose of the exercise. Each
150 probability obtained was averaged across the experts to obtain a consensus network dynamic. All
151 five spreadsheets used to construct a consensus network are included with the current submission
152 as Supplementary_Data_1. We appreciate that it may be difficult for experts to state with any
153 certainty that a network member will change state with an absolute probability of, say, 0.050 and
154 not 0.075, in a week’s time, and that it is probably easier to assess the *relative* likelihood of state
155 change between different scenarios. For that reason we suggest readers focus on relative and not
156 absolute population levels of different agroecosystem members when assessing population dynamic
157 phenomena, such as those displayed in the population dynamic plots of Figure 2.

158 Algorithmically, the operation of the model is very simple: in each time iteration of the model, each
159 node is assessed in relation to its current state and the state of all other nodes that influence it i.e.,
160 through network “edges” (arrows in Figure 1). Each node, given its current state and the state of
161 influencer nodes, accesses the relevant Boolean logic statement and changes its state with the
162 probability indicated therein. All nodes are updated in this way to enter the next time iteration and
163 the whole process is repeated over the specified number of time iterations of the model. Here we
164 use 26 weekly time intervals to represent the English Spring-Summer-Autumn growing season and
165 all simulations are initiated from what we assume to be a common starting state for arable systems
166 in spring: yield/crop growth high or satisfactory and all other ecosystem members (see Figure 1) low.

167 The current article introduces the innovation to the model described above of “converting” the
168 organic system to conventional by simulating the use of pesticides. Ten thousand replicate
169 simulations of any scenario are run. By quantifying the proportion of these networks showing “high”
170 (i.e. = 1) expression at any time for each network member, this produces a smooth network
171 population dynamic. When the proportion of these 10,000 simulations expressing high (as opposed
172 to low) hits a certain “threshold” for the pest under consideration, expression of the pest in all
173 10,000 replicates is set to low to simulate elimination through pesticide use. The pest under
174 consideration is then allowed to freely increase in incidence until it reaches threshold when it is
175 eliminated again, and so on. The single network replicate can be considered analogous to farmer-
176 perceived population dynamics at the single field level and the smoothed dynamic can be considered
177 similar to smoothed regional dynamics across multiple fields. By extension, the pesticide
178 intervention threshold represents the proportion of fields at farm or regional level showing a high,
179 unfavourable level of the focal pest. This assessment of multiple fields for “good” or “bad” pest
180 levels is probably a fair reflection of how the conscientious farmer might assess their fields for the
181 need to spray. Pseudocode describing this probabilistic Boolean regulatory network algorithm,
182 including pesticide intervention procedures, is included in the Supplementary Information.

183 The following scenarios are modelled: 1) No intervention (no pesticide use; the procedure just
184 described is not implemented) 2) Crop disease intervention (crop disease is reduced to zero
185 incidence at threshold, simulating, for example, fungicide use), 3) Crop pest intervention (crop pest
186 insects and their insect natural enemies are assumed and simultaneously reduced to zero incidence
187 at threshold, simulating non-selective insecticide use), 4) Crop weed intervention (crop weeds are
188 reduced to zero incidence at threshold, simulating selective, post-emergence herbicide use (AHDB,
189 2024) or post emergence mechanical intervention), 5) Full intervention (intervention to eliminate
190 disease, weeds, and pest/pest natural enemies implemented when each reaches threshold. Here,
191 each ecosystem pest must reach the threshold before intervention for that particular pest is
192 triggered; one pest reaching threshold does not trigger intervention for all). Simulations for all
193 combinations of dual pesticide applications were also run and are presented in the Supplementary
194 Information. Here, threshold triggering assumptions were as for full intervention.

195 Clearly, aspects of this treatment of pest control in English arable crops are highly simplified. The use
196 of generic terms such as “crop weeds” and “crop disease” and so on during expert parameterisation
197 of the model increases its scope and appeal but means that the threshold-based modelling approach
198 taken does not capture all aspects of control of these classes of pest. For example, pre-drilling
199 herbicide use in UK arable is not typically threshold based or selective (AHDB, 2024). Crop diseases
200 may include viruses and other microorganisms that are not easily treated by human intervention.
201 And so on. Perhaps most simple of all, however, is our treatment of pesticides with respect to active
202 compound degradation and cross kingdom, non-target effects. To simplify the modelling process we
203 assume that active pesticide compounds degrade rapidly into harmless ones and that pesticides

204 targeting one pest have no cross-kingdom effects (non-target effects on distantly related taxa e.g.
205 herbicide effects on insects) on other ecosystem members. There is, of course, a vast body of
206 evidence that these assumptions are commonly not true (reviewed in Bamal et al. (2024); Sabzevari
207 and Hofman (2022)). Any tree benefits demonstrated with pesticide use in the current article are,
208 therefore, likely to be “best case scenario”.

209 We quantified the benefits of trees by running the above scenarios and quantifying the proportion
210 of simulations showing high/satisfactory crop yield expression after 26 weeks with and without
211 trees. The difference in high yield proportion with and without trees was expressed as a proportion
212 of high yield proportion without trees. In more intuitive terms, the proportional or percentage boost
213 to crop yield through introduction of trees was assessed. Intervention thresholds between 0 and 1 in
214 steps of 0.1 were considered.

215 Links are provided with this article to download Supplementary Information (Supplementary
216 Information v1pt1.docx), expert spreadsheets used to parameterise the model
217 (Supplementary_data_1.zip) and code and data files used to drive the main model (Model_code.zip).

218
219 Figure 1. A network diagram showing the agroecosystem modelled. Nodes contain the principal
220 ecosystem members considered and edges (arrows) show the influence of nodes on each other.
221 Arrowheads show the direction of influence. The red arrow is the direct influence of trees on crop
222 yield. This is the subject of major biophysical models of agroforestry and is systematically omitted
223 from the current model. Figure and caption reproduced with modifications from Tosh et al. (2024).

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227 **Results**

228 With no pesticide intervention arable yield enjoys a boost of approximately 60% due to trees. (Figure
229 2 Part A). Crops show a reduced incidence of disease and pests in the presence of trees and an
230 increase in natural enemy numbers (Figure 2 Parts B and C). The use of herbicide gives an even
231 greater tree-related boost in crop yield with crops showing an 80% increase in yield at intervention
232 thresholds below 0.7 (Figure 2 Part D). When crop disease is kept low by regular elimination, the
233 benefit of trees is substantially reduced (a 10-20% yield improvement at lower thresholds – Figure 2
234 Part G) with remaining benefits presumably associated with increased natural enemy provision and
235 lower crop pest numbers (Figure 2 Parts H and I). When pests and their natural enemies are
236 eliminated the benefits of trees are substantially reduced (to around 20% yield improvement at
237 lower intervention ranges) (Figure 2 Part J).

238 Under full pesticide intervention at low thresholds, unsurprisingly, trees provide no boost to crop
239 yield through biotic mechanisms (Figure 2 Part M). It is notable, however, that this conclusion
240 applies even at high intervention thresholds (up to 0.7). This means that even if interventions are
241 applied late in the growing season, a full intervention treatment of pesticides largely nullifies any
242 benefits of trees.

243 Impacts of dual combinations of the various pesticides are presented in the Supplementary
244 Information (Supplementary Information v1pt1.docx). Effects are similar to those presented here in
245 that pesticide use tends to substantially reduce the yield benefits of in field trees. It should be noted,
246 however, that the combination of weeds and pest - pest natural enemy intervention gives the lowest
247 reductions in tree-related yield benefits i.e. is the least 'harmful'.

249

250 Figure 2. Proportional arable crop yield gain through the introduction of in-field trees under various
251 scenarios of pesticide intervention. Plots in blue bars show proportional yield gain across a number
252 of pesticide intervention thresholds. Line charts show the dynamics of pests, natural enemies, and
253 crop yield at a threshold of 0.2. The repeats of simulations at different “threshold” values in Part A
254 (no intervention) show the level of inherent stochastic variation between simulations. “Level” on the
255 y-axis of population dynamic plots, more precisely, is the proportion of 10,000 stochastic simulation
256 repeats that show high expression (i.e. = 1) at the relevant network node.

257

258 Discussion and conclusions

259 Here we return to the questions posed in the introduction of this article: Can growers still expect to
260 receive biotic ecosystem services from trees if they use pesticides, even in a selective way? What
261 pesticide interventions least and most negate tree-based ecosystem services? Will increasing
262 application thresholds improve ecosystem service provision if growers are using pesticides?
263 Simulations predict that trees *can* still benefit crops but results are highly dependent on the
264 intervention undertaken. Intervention to remove weeds appears largely harmless (in fact it is
265 beneficial) in terms of yield-related ecosystem services offered by trees, but intervention for
266 diseases or for pest insects negatively impacts tree benefits. Interventions against two pests
267 throughout the growing season universally reduces tree benefits to the crop, but the least harmful
268 dual combination is for weeds and insects. Lastly, triple intervention against all associates of trees
269 renders trees of no benefit to crop yield. In general, these predictions are robust to intervention
270 thresholds across ranges that would typically be considered by growers. If we consider thresholds,
271 whose range is 0-1, analogous to the proportion of a farmer’s field that are showing high incidence
272 of the pest under consideration, the above predictions are generally robust up to around 0.6. This is
273 likely considerably higher than would be considered by most growers. Growers who use thresholds
274 above around 0.6 may retain much of the benefits of trees but are likely to lower the benefit of their
275 pesticide intervention as the pest will have exerted significant negative effects on the crop. This
276 relationship between intervention threshold, tree benefits, and pesticide benefits to yield is likely to
277 be complex and warrants further investigation. There may be some scenarios where it might be
278 beneficial for growers to delay pest intervention because the increase in tree benefits this brings
279 compensates for potential yield lost due to intervention delay.

280 With no pesticide intervention natural enemies may decrease pest numbers which may in turn
281 decrease the incidence of plant diseases such as viruses that insect pests spread. In addition, experts
282 may feel that tree rows act as a physical barrier to the spread of other plant diseases such as fungal
283 disease. Little is known of such effects but they have been reported in the field (Beule et al., 2019).
284 When herbicide was used, the dynamics of the system with and without trees was generally similar
285 to the dynamics without intervention suggesting that experts consider weeds to be relatively
286 isolated pests that are an increased burden in the presence of trees (presumably proliferating in
287 understories) and whose removal in the presence of trees can further boost yield. Crop yield in the
288 model is very sensitive to crop disease (Tosh et al., 2024) and experts clearly feel that trees reduce
289 the spread of crop disease as there is very little remaining benefit to the presence of trees in the
290 disease intervention scenario. In the case where insect pests and their natural enemies are
291 eliminated there is substantially more crop disease in the absence of trees so experts clearly believe
292 that diseases other than insect borne diseases (typically viruses) can be constrained by in-field tree
293 rows.

294 Crop disease is clearly crucial to the dynamics of our model and its predictions in the current
295 context. Tosh et al. (2024) showed that the crop yield in the model (parameterised with one fewer
296 expert) was most sensitive to this pest and it is clear in the current study that any intervention
297 involving crop disease interventions dramatically reduces the benefits of trees. Experts appear to
298 feel that trees can slow the spread of crop disease, perhaps through the provision of natural
299 enemies that eat insect disease vectors, but also by other mechanisms such as the providing a
300 physical barrier to disease spread. Little is known of this area. One study has looked at the incidence
301 of fungal diseases in agroforestry and monoculture in German oilseed rape and cereals. They found
302 little difference with the exception that that colonisation of oilseed rape with *Verticillium*
303 *longisporum* and wheat with the head blight pathogen *Fusarium tricinctum* was lower in
304 agroforestry than in monoculture (Beule et al., 2019). Agroforestry can be considered a special case
305 of intercropping and there is more information on the incident of disease in intercropping systems vs
306 monoculture in the literature from this area. Here intercrops (if carefully chosen) generally reduce
307 the incidence of crop disease through mechanisms such as reducing exposed soil and the likelihood
308 of splash-dispersed and soilborne disease, suppressing virus vectors, diluting the pool of available
309 crop hosts and introducing allelopathic compounds (Huss et al., 2022). As the current model “grows”
310 through the contribution of further expert input and input of field data it will be particularly
311 important to focus on disease dynamics in the parameterisation process to ensure the model
312 provides the most reliable output.

313 Another study (Jones et al., 2023) has recently taken a similar conceptual approach to the current
314 article by analysing the literature to determine how yield-related ecosystem services can be
315 maximised when diversifying at field level through practices such as silvoarable agroforestry. Their
316 findings broadly agree with ours in that agrochemical use is assumed to lessen the benefits of
317 diversification and tip the balance of diversification impacts towards yield suppression. Other
318 practices that Jones et al. (2023) found to increase the likely hood of diversification boosting yield
319 include: joint crop and animal production, using multiple combined diversification practices such as
320 intercropping and cover crops, undertaking diversification in temperate climates, and scenarios
321 where diversification enhanced belowground taxa.

322 We have clearly been “generous” in our treatment of pesticides in this paper, principally to keep the
323 model simple and elegant. Many pesticides do not break down rapidly into harmless compounds and
324 may linger in the environment, impacting target pests and other organisms for long periods
325 (Sabzevari and Hofman, 2022). This is perhaps of least concern in our treatment of pesticides as
326 environmental persistence and its impact on the pest can be considered analogous to lowering of
327 thresholds. The assumption of absence of non-target effects across kingdoms is potentially more
328 serious. Glyphosate, for example, is known to impact numerous physiological processes in non-
329 target insects with implications for foraging behaviour in the field (studies reviewed in (Bartling et
330 al., 2024)). Crop fungicides can impact soil microbial composition with potential implications for the
331 weed-crop balance (Bartling et al., 2024). Impact of these non-target effects on dynamics of the
332 ecological network are difficult to predict but effects are presumably suppressive and reduce the
333 benefits of tree-associated organisms to crop yield. Effects shown in this paper are, therefore, likely
334 to be “best case scenarios” associated with pest interventions. As only a fraction of the interventions
335 considered here show no or limited negative impact on tree benefits, we find it difficult to
336 recommend pesticide use to agroforesters who are serious about getting the most from ecosystems
337 services. It also goes without saying the pesticides negatively impact much of the remainder of
338 nature that has little impact on the growth of crops.

339 Nevertheless, pesticide use is widespread, and the global growth of agroforestry in the coming years
340 is likely to occur in the face of widespread pesticide use. For growers who are prepared to use
341 pesticides selectively and with restraint, the current paper provides some suggestions on how
342 negative impacts to tree ecosystem services can be reduced in English silvoarable systems.
343 Restrained herbicide use alone may have minimal impacts on tree benefits. All broader, double
344 interventions across the growing season will reduce tree ecosystem services but the intervention for
345 weeds and insects least so. Intervention for all pests considered here (weeds, insects and crop
346 disease) is not recommended and nullifies all ecosystem services, even at high intervention
347 thresholds. This paper may be of particular use to growers in the area of regenerative agriculture
348 where selective and minimal use of pesticides is permitted (Rempelos et al. 2023; Soil Association
349 2024).

350

351 Author Declarations

352 Submission declaration

353 • the work described has not been published previously except in the form of a preprint, an
354 abstract, a published lecture, academic thesis or registered report. See our policy on
355 multiple, redundant or concurrent publication.

356

357 • the article is not under consideration for publication elsewhere.

358

359 • the article's publication is approved by all authors and tacitly or explicitly by the responsible
360 authorities where the work was carried out.

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362 • if accepted, the article will not be published elsewhere in the same form, in English or in any
363 other language, including electronically without the written consent of the copyright-holder.

364

365 Authors' contributions

366 CRT: study concept; model construction; coding and parameterisation; running simulations; writing
367 of manuscript; revision of manuscript.

368 JS: Expert input and model parameterisation; reviewed first draft of MS and provided comments that
369 lead to substantial revision.

370

371 Declaration of interests

372 The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

373

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377

378 Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

379 Generative AI has not been used to write the text or create the figures of this paper, with the
380 exception of one image included in the graphical abstract, which is clearly labelled as AI generated.
381 AI played no part in the coding process.

382

383 Supplementary materials

384 A MS Word document of “Supplementary Information v1pt1.docx” can be downloaded at
385 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14846263>.

386 A zipped file of completed expert spreadsheets, “Supplementary_data_1.zip”, can be downloaded at
387 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14826937>.

388 A zipped file of R scripts and data used to run the main model, “Model_code.zip”, can be
389 downloaded at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14827028>.

390

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